

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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FINANCIAL MECHANISMS OF SUPPORTING TEXTILE PRODUCTS EXPORT

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Abstract: Comprehensive measures are being implemented in our country to develop the textile and sewing-knitting industry, to support the investment and export activities of enterprises in the sector. Privileges given by our state to support entrepreneurs create an opportunity for further development of this industry. The article examines the President's decision to promote the development of the textile industry and exports. As part of the textile industry support funds and information about its significance, industrial production and some economic indicators.

Key words: Textiles, export, credit, preferential period, trading houses.

Annotatsiya: Mamlakatimizda to'qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatini rivojlantirish, soha korxonalarining investitsiya va eksport faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Davlatimiz tomonidan tadbirkorlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida berilayotgan imtiyozlar bu soxani yanada rivojlanishiga imkoniyat yaratmoqda. Maqolada Prezidentning to'qimachilik sanoati va eksportini rivojlantirishga ko'maklashish to'g'risidagi qarori o'rganilgan. To'qimachilik sanoatining ishlab chiqarishi imkoniyatlari va ayrim iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: To'qimachilik, eksport, kredit, imtiyozli davr, savdo uylari.

Аннотация: В нашей стране реализуются комплексные меры по развитию текстильной и швейно-трикотажной промышленности, поддержке инвестиционной и экспортной деятельности предприятий отрасли. Льготы, предоставляемые нашим государством для поддержки предпринимателей, создают возможность для дальнейшего развития этой отрасли. В статье рассматривается решение Президента о содействии развитию текстильной промышленности и экспорта. В рамках фонда поддержки текстильной промышленности представлена информация о ее значении, промышленном производстве и некоторых экономических показателях.

Ключевые слова: Текстиль, экспорт, кредит, льготный период, торговые дома.

INTRODUCTION

The share of industrial products in the gross domestic product of Uzbekistan is growing day by day. In particular, the share of textile products in the export of industrial products is significant. According to preliminary data, the GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-December 2022 at current prices will be 888,341.7 billion. amounted to soums and increased by 5.7% in interest compared to the corresponding period of 2021. The industrial sector made the biggest contribution to the growth of GDP, it made 5.2%, of which the volume of production of textile products increased by 9.8%.

As a result of the implementation of complex measures for the development of the textile and sewing-knitting industry in our country, as well as for the support of investment and export activities of industry enterprises, 45% of cotton fiber and yarn produced in the republic is being processed, as well as the annual export potential of the industry exceeded 3.2 billion dollars. At the same time, increased competition in world markets, and cost reduction due to the production of mixed products by foreign manufacturers require additional measures for the development of this sector.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Many economists from abroad and our republic have researched the theoretical foundations of sustainable development of textile industry enterprises. S.H. Abdullayeva and G.M. Davlyatova stated that "textile industry enterprises are faced with such a global problem as the introduction of successive stages of raw material pro-

cessing cycles necessary for products in demand on the world market, and this process is based mainly on the following. The scheme for processing raw materials is carried out according to primary processing (semi-finished products) - materials ready for industrial production - products ready for final consumption.

Among the scientists who conducted research on the problems of development of the textile industry, there are also Artykov A.O., R.S. Muratov, Jalalova I.A., Makhmudov E.Kh., Oripov S.Sh., Isakov M.Yu., Yuldasheva Sh., Karabaeva G.Sh., Nazhimdinov R.D. and others.¹

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research work used several research methods to search, identify and analyze issues of using the country's tourism potential to ensure economic stability. In particular, based on statistical data, a comparative analysis of the development indicators of tourist sites in Uzbekistan was carried out. The issues of using tourism opportunities in our country were studied and discussed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the next five years, through deep processing of cotton fiber, to increase the production volume of high-added-value finished products, textile products by 2.1 times and the export rate by 2.6 times, and to produce carpets and home textile products. it was achieved to bring the release to a new level.

According to preliminary data, in January-December 2022, 551.1 trillion will be spent by republican enterprises. Soms worth of industrial products were produced, and compared to January-December 2021, the physical volume index of industrial production was 105.2%. In particular, in January-December 2022, the share of textile production was 13.7%, the physical volume index increased by 9.8%, and the production volume was 62,757.0 billion. amounting to soums.

In January-December 2022, the share of the clothing industry in the manufacturing industry is 3.8%, the physical volume index is 105.5%, and the production volume is 17,210.1 billion. amounted to soum.

During the year, 532 types of textile products were exported to 69 countries of the world by the total enterprises of our country. Among exported textile products, cotton yarn accounted for 45.2%, ready-made knitwear and sewing clothes for 28.5%. 2,899.5 million by the end of January-November this year. Exports of textile products in US dollars accounted for 16.7% of total exports and increased by 9.5% compared to last year. The main export of textile products includes cotton yarn, ready-made knitwear and sewing clothes, embroidered fabrics, cotton gauze, silk and silk products, cotton products and carpets.

Among the countries that purchase textile products, the largest share is the Russian Federation at 1,156 million US dollars, 41% of the total export volume, Turkey at 481.9 million US dollars, 21.8%, the Kyrgyz Republic at 457.9 thousand US dollars, China 253.1 million US dollars, Iran with 74.9 million US dollars, Poland with 73.2 million US dollars. To support the activities of cotton-textile clusters, fundamentally reform the textile and sewing-knitting industry, and further increase the export potential of the industry, several decree decisions are being adopted by the head of our state. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-2 of January 10, 2023:

By the end of 2023, by the end of 2023, by the Ministry of Investments, Industry and Trade, the textile and sewing-knitting industry of the "Uzto'qimachilik sanoat" association will be supported by the state on a large scale. the tasks of increasing the utilization of production facilities from 65% to 81%, filling 35 thousand vacancies, including employing to the population registered in the social registers.

To the Export Support Fund under the Export Promotion Agency for continuous provision of working capital, including revolving funds, by the Recovery and Development Fund to enterprises exporting gauze, knitted fabric and ready-made sewing and knitting products, according to his order, funds in the amount of 200 million US dollars were allocated for a period of 3 years at an annual rate of 4 percent.

If enterprises exporting textile products accept obligations to ensure export in the amount of 50% of the total volume of their manufactured products, the credit should be set at least 30% of their funds, including buildings and structures, and working capital. If it is confirmed that there are no overdue debts in terms of obligations, in commercial banks, based on their order, in the amount of 100 million US dollars, for a period of 10 years, with a 3-year grace period at an annual rate of 4 percent and for the rest of the period at an annual rate of 5 percent, gas, carpeting, the opening of credit lines for production projects of dyeing-finishing, ready-made sewing-knitting products has been established. However, if the export obligation is not fulfilled by the enterprise, the interest rates calculated during the preferential period of the loan will be recalculated at an annual rate of 5 percent.

¹ A.Yu. Mardanov. To'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarini barqaror rivojlantirish omillari. yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot. 2024-yi.yanvar. №1 son.

The annual interest rate set by commercial banks for loans allocated from the resources of the Recovery and Development Fund has been set at an amount not exceeding 1 percent. Also, to encourage the export of textile products, commercial banks will provide working capital to textile and sewing-knitting enterprises through revolving credit in the amount of 1 trillion soums for 24 months, including a 6-month grace period of no more than 2%. loans are allocated using bank margins.

According to the decree of the President, the demand for a month advance payment for electricity consumption for textile and sewing-knitting enterprises has been canceled. The Export Promotion Agency will reimburse 50 percent of the costs of introducing financial reporting to textile and sewing-knitting enterprises based on international standards, but no more than \$25,000. In this case, it was determined that these costs would be covered by the enterprise after attracting debt funds from international financial institutions and foreign commercial banks in the established order.

Financial resources in the following amounts will be allocated for up to 3 years, based on the volume of exports made during the last 12 months, from the account of the export support fund for textile enterprises:

- when the export volume is up to 5 million dollars - up to 1 million dollars;
- when the export volume is from 5 million to 10 million dollars - up to 2 million dollars;
- when the export volume is from 10 million to 15 million dollars - up to 3 million dollars;
- when the export volume is from 15 million to 20 million dollars - up to 4 million dollars;
- when the export volume exceeds 20 million dollars - up to 5 million dollars.

It is envisaged that textile and sewing-knitting enterprises will be allowed to transfer funds up to 100,000 US dollars per year for the establishment of a trading house and store abroad without separate decisions.

CONCLUSIONS

The financial resources allocated to support exports in textiles have a positive effect on the further development of the production environment, the expansion of the scale of production, the creation of new jobs, and the increase of the product range to world standards. I believe that it will lead to an increase in the volume of exports of suitable competitive textile products.

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